

1 **Cross-resistance to alternative second-line Apalutamide**
2 **treatment in Castration Resistance Prostate Cancer cellular**
3 **models**

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26 **Abstract**

27 **Background/Objectives:** The treatment of choice for prostate cancer is
28 androgen deprivation (ADT) and novel hormonal agents such as abiraterone,
29 Enzalutamide or Apalutamide. Initially, this therapy is highly effective, but a
30 significant challenge arises as most patients eventually develop resistance,
31 resulting in castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC). Furthermore, the
32 sequential use of these drugs can lead to cross-resistance, diminishing their
33 efficacy. Tumor heterogeneity plays a pivotal role in the development of
34 resistance to different treatments. This study utilized cellular models of CRPC to
35 assess the response to Apalutamide when it is administered as a second- or third-
36 line treatment.

37 **Methods:** Functional and genetic analyses were conducted in various CRPC cell
38 models exposed to Apalutamide. These analyses included real-time cell
39 monitoring assays, flow cytometry, clonogenicity assays, and RT-qPCR.

40 **Results:** CRPC cell models were capable of continued proliferation, maintained
41 cell cycle profiles similar to those of untreated cells, and retained their clonogenic
42 potential. Cross-resistance to Apalutamide in models of ADT, ADT plus
43 Enzalutamide, or Abiraterone resistance did not correlate with the expression
44 levels of *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* variants. Gene expression analysis of resistant
45 prostate cancer cell lines revealed that treatment with Apalutamide induced the
46 emergence of more aggressive phenotypes, including cancer stem cells or
47 neuroendocrine differentiation profiles.

48 **Conclusions:** Most CRPC cell models develop cross-resistance to Apalutamide
49 and are able to proliferate and retain their clonogenic capability. Apalutamide
50 resistance is not linked to the expression of *AR-V7* or *AR-V9* variants but is
51 instead associated to the emergence of more aggressive expression profiles.

52

53 **Keywords:** Prostate cancer; Androgen deprivation therapy (ADT); castration-
54 resistant prostate cancer (CRPC); Abiraterone; Enzalutamide; Apalutamide.

55 **Introduction**

56 Prostate cancer (PCa) is the most frequently diagnosed tumor in nonsmoking
57 men worldwide and the fifth leading cause of cancer-related death(1). PCa
58 progression is significantly influenced by androgen signaling through the
59 androgen receptor (AR), which regulates the proliferation and growth of both
60 healthy and cancerous prostate tissue(2).

61 Owing to this pivotal role, most current therapies are designed to target this
62 pathway. In this context, the treatment of choice for PCa is androgen deprivation
63 therapy (ADT)(3). This therapy is initially very effective; however, most patients
64 eventually develop resistance to this treatment, a condition known as castration-
65 resistant prostate cancer (CRPC)(4,5). These patients are subsequently treated
66 with next-generation hormonal agents (NHAs), including Abiraterone acetate
67 (AA), Enzalutamide (Enz) and Apalutamide (Apa)(3,6). AA is an antiandrogen
68 that inhibits testosterone synthesis via the inhibition of 17 α -hydroxylase
69 (CYP17)(7). In contrast, Enz and Apa are competitive inhibitors of the AR that act
70 by binding to the ligand binding domain (LBD) of the AR and preventing its
71 translocation and binding to the DNA necessary for AR activation(8,9). However,
72 these treatments also fail, as most patients have acquired common resistance
73 mechanisms, and consequently, tumor progression continues. In addition, the
74 use of these drugs sequentially generates cross-resistance, which results in a
75 decrease in their effectiveness(7,8). Therefore, the benefits of the use of
76 combination therapies, rather than their sequential use, are currently being
77 studied(10–13).

78 Different mechanisms of resistance to ADT have been described, and among
79 them, the expression of variants of the androgen receptor (AR-Vs) is of particular
80 importance(14). One of the isoforms most frequently found in prostate tumors is
81 *AR-V7*(15–18), which has recently been shown to be coexpressed with the *AR-*
82 *V9* variant(19). Likewise, tumor heterogeneity also plays a fundamental role in
83 the acquisition of resistance to different treatments(20). Increasing evidence
84 suggests that prolonged inhibition of the AR pathway may alter the course of the
85 disease, leading to histological dedifferentiation and alterations in the cell lineage
86 in the form of tumor stem cells (CSCs), epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT)
87 or neuroendocrine differentiation (NE)(21).

88 Knowing the molecular mechanisms involved in resistance to androgen
89 deprivation therapies would allow us to predict the effectiveness of these new
90 therapies and establish a new line of therapeutic action beneficial to PCa patients.
91 Therefore, the main aim of this work was to evaluate the response to the use of
92 Apa as second- or third-line treatment, using the basis of cellular models of PCa
93 resistant to the most common androgen deprivation therapies (R-ADT, R-ADT/E
94 and R-ADT/AA). We evaluated the proliferation rates and cell cycle, AR
95 expression levels, clonogenicity ability and expression of phenotypic markers
96 among the different CRPC models under Apa treatment.

97 **METHODS**

98 **Cell Culture**

99 Two different human PCa cell lines obtained from the American Type Culture
100 Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA) were used as controls: LNCaP (an
101 androgen-sensitive adenocarcinoma cell line derived from supraclavicular lymph
102 node metastasis) and 22RV1 (a cell line derived from an androgen-dependent
103 CWR22 xenograft after castration-induced regression and relapse). Castration
104 resistance cellular models were generated from these cell lines as previously
105 described (22). All the cell lines were maintained in RPMI 1640 medium (Sigma-
106 Aldrich, Merck, St. Louis, MO, USA) supplemented with 1% Penicillin-
107 Streptomycin Solution 100X ((Biowest, Nuaille, France) and 10% fetal bovine
108 serum (FBS) for the WT cell lines, while the castration-resistant cellular models
109 used charcoal-stripped fetal bovine serum (CSS) in a humidified incubator at
110 37°C with 5% CO₂. Concomitant ADT-NHA-resistant PCa cell lines (R-ADT/E and
111 R-ADT/AA) were grown in the presence of Enz (40 µM) or AA (20 µM),
112 respectively. All the cell lines were routinely tested for mycoplasma contamination
113 using the Venor®GeM qEP (Minerva Biolabs, Dublin, Ireland) and authenticated
114 via STR profiling using AmpFLSTR® Identifiler® Plus (Applied Biosystems,
115 Thermo Fisher Scientific, Maltham, MA, USA), ensuring the presence of
116 mycoplasma-free and STR-validated cells.

117 **Treatment with Apalutamide as second-line therapy**

118 The IC50 value for Apa in LNCaP WT cells was determined via MTT assays
119 (Sigma-Aldrich, Merck). Briefly, in 96-well plates, 1.5×10^4 cells per well were
120 seeded. After 24 hours, the cells were treated with decreasing concentrations of
121 Apa (0.5, 0.25, 0.125, 0.0625, 0.0312, 0.0156, 0.0078, 0.0039, 0.0019 and
122 0.00097 μM) for 3 to 5 days. To measure cell viability, the medium was removed,
123 and 100 μL of MTT reagent diluted in PBS was added to each well. After a 3-hour
124 incubation, the resulting formazan crystals were dissolved by adding 100 μL of
125 DMSO (Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The absorbance was then
126 measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm using a Tecan Infinite 200 Pro
127 microplate reader (Tecan Trader AG, Männedorf, Switzerland). The IC50 values
128 were calculated by plotting dose-response curves using GraphPad Prism™
129 software (version 8.0 for Windows, San Diego, USA). WT and ADT/NHA-resistant
130 cell lines were treated with IC50 for 5 days for proliferation, plating, cell cycle and
131 colony formation assays.

132 **Cell Proliferation Assays**

133 The effects of Apa on the proliferation and doubling time of both sensitive and
134 resistant cell lines were evaluated via real-time cell monitoring assays (RTCA)
135 (xCELLigence; ACEA Biosciences, Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). The cells were
136 monitored over 5 days, and the impedance was recorded as a measure of the
137 cell index (CI). At least four experimental replicates were performed for each
138 experimental condition, and the results were analyzed in GraphPad Prism™.

139 To calculate the doubling time, xCELLigence Cell Index (CI) values over time are
140 used to fit an exponential growth curve as indicated by the manufacturer. The
141 doubling time is then determined using the standard equation:

$$142 \quad \text{Doubling time} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\text{slope of the exponential regression}}$$

143 The slope is obtained by performing exponential fitting of the CI growth curve
144 specifically during the logarithmic phase of cell growth.

145 The normalized doubling time is calculated by dividing the doubling time of Apa-
146 treated cells by the doubling time of their corresponding untreated controls for

147 each cell line. This normalization process allows for a standardized comparison
148 across all PCa cell lines, accounting for their inherent growth rates.

149 **Sequential Passage Cell Proliferation Monitoring Assay**

150 1×10^5 cells per well were seeded in 6-well plates and treated with 0.130 μM Apa
151 for 5 days. Following treatment, cells were detached, counted, and replated in the
152 presence of Apa. This process was repeated over three consecutive passages.
153 Each experimental condition was performed with a minimum of four replicates,
154 and the data were analyzed using GraphPad Prism™.

155 **Cell cycle experiments**

156 Following Apa treatment, the cell cycle was assessed. The cells were dissociated
157 after 5 days of culture, washed with PBS and fixed in ice-cold 70% ethanol.
158 Following overnight incubation at -20°C , the cells were incubated with propidium
159 iodide buffer (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ propidium iodide, 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ RNase, 0.05% NP-40, 3 mM
160 EDTA pH 8.0 in PBS) and analyzed using a BD FACSVerser™ (BD Biosciences,
161 Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA). The fluorescence intensity representing ploidy (2N and
162 4N) was used to assess the G_0/G_1 and G_2/M phases, respectively, using
163 BDFACSuite™, ModFit LT™ and GraphPad Prism™ software.

164 **Quantification of *AR Full-Length*, *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* expression.**

165 Total RNA was extracted post-Apa treatment via TRI Reagent (Life
166 Technologies). The RNA concentration and purity were determined using a
167 NanoDrop 2000c Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), and reverse
168 transcription was performed with 1 μg of total RNA via the Transcriptor First
169 Strand cDNA Synthesis Kit ((Thermo Fisher Scientific). qPCR was conducted
170 using iTaq Universal SYBR Green Supermix in an HT7900 Fast Real-Time PCR
171 System (Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific) using custom primers
172 (Supplementary Table S1). Relative expression ($2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}}$) was calculated against
173 GAPDH. The experiments were performed in triplicate (mean \pm standard error
174 mean (SEM)), and the results were statistically analyzed via Student's t tests.

175 **Phenotypic marker expression**

176 qPCR analysis of cancer stem cell (CSC), epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition
177 (EMT), and neuroendocrine (NE) marker expression was performed following
178 established methods and primers (Supplementary Table S1). Five genes for each
179 phenotype were analyzed and plotted in sensitive and resistant cell lines. The
180 experiments were performed in triplicate (mean \pm SEM) as previously described.

181 **Clonogenic Assays**

182 Clonogenicity was assessed in 22RV1- and LNCaP-resistant models. The cells
183 were seeded (800 or 1000 cells/well), treated with Apa for 5 days, and cultured
184 for 12 days after treatment with fresh medium. Colonies were fixed in 70% ice-
185 cold ethanol for 15 minutes and stained with 0.05% crystal violet solution. The
186 wells were washed 3 times with water and allowed to dry completely. The
187 clonogenic capability was quantified with an Odyssey infrared imaging system
188 (LI-COR Biosciences; Lincoln, NE, USA) for area and colony counts. Three
189 experimental replicates were performed for each experimental condition.

190 **Statistical analysis**

191 The data are presented as the means \pm SD or SEM. Statistical comparisons were
192 performed via unpaired Student's t test and one-way ANOVA plus Dunnett's
193 multiple comparisons test or two-way ANOVA plus Bonferroni's multiple
194 comparisons test. All the statistical analyses and graph plotting were conducted
195 via GraphPad Prism. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

196 **RESULTS**

197 **Proliferation Analysis of CRPC models in Response to Apalutamide.**

198 To establish a standard concentration of Apa for treating all resistant cell models,
199 the IC₅₀ values were determined using the most sensitive WT cell line, LNCaP.
200 An MTT assay was conducted over 3 to 5 days, testing a wide range of Apa
201 concentrations spanning from 0.5 to 0.00097 μ M. (**Figure 1**). The IC₅₀ for Apa
202 was determined using GraphPad Prism™ software, ranging from 0.088 μ M at 3

203 days to 0.130 μ M at 5 days. All subsequent experiments and analyses were
204 conducted by treating all the cell lines with these concentrations.

205 Next, the different cell lines were treated with 0.130 μ M Apa for 5 days. When the
206 effect of Apa exposure was studied, it was observed that, in the case of LNCaP
207 cells, all the resistant cell lines (LNCaP R-ADT, LNCaP R-ADT/E and LNCaP R-
208 ADT/AA) presented greater proliferation rates than did the LNCaP WT line
209 ($p < 0.001$). However, the sensitivity to such treatment was different in the different
210 cell lines analyzed. In the LNCaP R-ADT line, Apa administration significantly
211 reduced the cell proliferation rate (60% vs. 100%). Notably, in the Enz-resistant
212 line (LNCaP R-ADT/E), whose mechanism of action is similar to that of Apa, a
213 similar decrease in proliferation was also observed with respect to the untreated
214 line (59% vs. 100%). Surprisingly, the proliferation rate of the LNCaP R-ADT/AA
215 line treated with Apa barely decreased with respect to that of the same line
216 without treatment (90% vs. 100%) (**Figure 2A**).

217 Additionally, analysis of the doubling times derived from these proliferation curves
218 revealed a highly significant sensitivity of LNCaP WT cells to Apa treatment, with
219 a substantial increase of 9.47 compared to untreated cells. In contrast, the impact
220 of Apa on LNCaP CRPC models was more modest, with doubling time increases
221 ranging from 3.83 in LNCaP R-ADT cells to 2.07 in LNCaP R-ADT/AA cells
222 (**Figure 2B**).

223 The effects of Apa exposure on the resistance models of the 22RV1 cell line were
224 also analyzed. The analysis of cell proliferation in the 22RV1 R-ADT cell line
225 revealed the acquisition of cross-resistance to Apa, since the cells were able to
226 proliferate normally in the presence of Apa (114% vs. 100%, +/- Apa).
227 Furthermore, a highly significant increase in tolerance to Apa was observed with
228 respect to the 22RV1 WT cell line (114% vs. 50%) ($p < 0.001$). In contrast to what
229 was observed in the LNCaP lines, the concomitant 22RV1 R-ADT/E and 22RV1
230 R-ADT/AA models presented a similar sensitivity to Apa as the 22RV1 WT cell
231 line (54%, 52% vs. 50%) (**Figure 2C**).

232 In another analysis of cell proliferation, cell doubling time was evaluated in the
233 different cell lines in the presence of Apa with respect to the untreated lines. In
234 22RV1 cell lines, the reduction in doubling time due to Apa treatment was less

235 pronounced compared to LNCaP cell lines. Only the 22RV1 WT cells exhibited a
236 significant delay, with a doubling time increase of 1.73 relative to the untreated
237 control. The CRPC cellular models largely maintained their proliferation rates,
238 with values of 1.10 for 22RV1 R-ADT/E and 1.03 for 22RV1 R-ADT/AA cells,
239 respectively. Notably, the 22RV1 R-ADT cell line displayed an unexpected
240 response, increasing its proliferation rate under Apa exposure, as reflected by a
241 reduced doubling time of 0.89 (**Figure 2D**).

242 Next, 5-day cell cycle analysis revealed that LNCaP WT cells are initially sensitive
243 to Apa treatment alone. Exposure to Apa induced arrest in the G_0/G_1 phase
244 ($p < 0.05$); furthermore, this arrest was accompanied by the induction of cell death,
245 as detected by the presence of a sub- G_0 peak ($p < 0.05$). Surprisingly, the LNCaP
246 R-ADT/AA line, which was tolerant of Apa at the proliferation level, presented cell
247 cycle arrest at G_0/G_1 ($p < 0.01$) and slight induction of cell death (in the sub G_0
248 phase), as did the LNCaP WT line. In LNCaP R-ADT/E cells, there was no
249 statistically significant reduction in the number of cells in G_2/M , which was in
250 accordance with the decrease in proliferation described above (**Figure 2E**). In
251 contrast, LNCaP R-ADT cells presented a virtually unchanged cell cycle
252 distribution in the presence or absence of Apa (**Figure 2E**).

253 With respect to cell cycle analysis, 22RV1 WT cells were sensitive to exclusive
254 treatment with Apa. In this cell line, cell cycle arrest was observed in the G_0/G_1
255 phase ($p < 0.01$), which was not accompanied by cell death induction.
256 Interestingly, 22RV1 R-ADT cells presented a reduction in the percentage of cells
257 in G_2/M , which was compensated by an increase in the percentage of cells in S
258 phase. The remaining cell lines (22RV1 R-ADT/E and 22RV1 R-ADT/AA), which
259 are cross-resistant, presented an unaltered cell cycle distribution in the presence
260 of Apa (**Figure 2E**).

261 To determine the adhesion capability and the ability to resume proliferation under
262 continuous Apa treatment, sequential passage cell proliferation monitoring
263 assays were conducted during three consecutive passages. LNCaP WT cells, as
264 observed at the proliferation level, initially showed sensitivity to Apa, but as the
265 number of passages increased, their tolerance to treatment increased (0.6, 0.84
266 and 0.99) (**Figure 3A**). The behavior of the LNCaP resistance models varied
267 across lines. In the LNCaP R-ADT line, tolerance to Apa remained stable across

268 passages, consistently exceeding a normalized value of 1. Conversely, distinct
269 responses were observed in the LNCaP R-ADT/E and LNCaP R-ADT/AA lines.
270 In LNCaP R-ADT/E cells, the proliferation rate mirrored that of LNCaP WT cells,
271 increasing from the second passage onward. In contrast, the LNCaP R-ADT/AA
272 cells exhibited a progressive decrease in proliferation from the third passage
273 onward, indicating an enhanced sensitivity to Apa with increasing passage
274 number (**Figure 3A**).

275 On the other hand, in all 22RV1 cell lines that demonstrated some sensitivity to
276 Apa (22RV1 WT, 22RV1 R-ADT/E, and 22RV1 R-ADT/AA), sensitivity
277 consistently increased with successive passages. This effect was particularly
278 pronounced in the 22RV1 R-ADT/E line, where relative proliferation compared to
279 untreated cells decreased significantly across passages (1.44, 0.74 and 0.67,
280 respectively) (**Figure 3B**). In contrast, the proliferation rates for the 22RV1 R-
281 ADT line were comparable to those of the untreated line across all three
282 passages (0.67, 1.00 and 0.89). These findings suggest that the 22RV1 R-ADT
283 line maintains relative resistance to Apa, despite not having prior exposure to this
284 NHA (**Figure 3B**).

285 In summary, all together these results highlight the variable responses to Apa
286 treatment across different PCa cell models and underscore the complex nature
287 of antiandrogen resistance in CRPC.

288 **Colony-forming capability Analysis of CRPC models in Response to** 289 **Apalutamide.**

290 The colony-forming capability of the different cell lines in the presence of 0.130
291 μ M Apa was analyzed in relation to that of the untreated lines, considering
292 colonies from approximately 100 cells. The LNCaP WT line treated with Apa was
293 unable to form colonies. In the case of the LNCaP R-ADT line, a tendency toward
294 a greater number of colonies was observed, and the area of colony occupancy
295 was even greater than that in the untreated cells. Compared with the untreated
296 lines, the ADT resistance models and the second-line treatments (LNCaP R-
297 ADT/E and LNCaP R-ADT/AA) treated with Apa presented slight reductions in
298 both the number of colonies and area of occupation, with values of 56% ($p < 0.001$)
299 for the LNCaP R-ADT/E line and 70% for the LNCaP R-ADT/AA line (**Figure 4**).

300 Similarly, the resistance patterns of the 22RV1 lines were analyzed. In the 22RV1
301 WT line treated with Apa, no differences were observed in either the number of
302 colonies or the area of occupancy with respect to the untreated line. The 22RV1
303 R-ADT cells in the presence of Apa presented a similar number of colonies to the
304 untreated line; however, their area of occupancy was twice as large. The
305 clonogenic capability of the 22RV1 R-ADT/E and 22RV1 R-ADT/AA lines in the
306 presence of Apa did not significantly differ from that of the untreated lines in terms
307 of either the number of colonies or the area of colony occupancy. **(Figure 4).**

308 **Gene expression analysis of CRPC models in response to** 309 **Apalutamide.**

310 Next, we wanted to study the changes in gene expression that occurred in the
311 different cell lines upon treatment with 0.130 μ M Apa for 5 days. First, we
312 evaluated whether the presence of cross-resistance was related to the
313 transcriptional reactivation of AR. For this purpose, the gene expression of AR
314 and its variants *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* was analyzed in resistance models in
315 response to Apa. In both control cell lines (LNCaP WT and 22RV1 WT), which
316 were sensitive to Apa treatment at the proliferative level, this drug increased *AR*
317 *total* and *AR-FL* mRNA levels, whereas the *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* variants were not
318 expressed **(Figure 5).**

319 For the CRPC models, in both the LNCaP R-ADT line and the LNCaP R-ADT/E
320 line, none of the AR variants were expressed at the mRNA level. In contrast, the
321 LNCaP R-ADT/AA line presented increased expression of *AR total*, *AR-FL* and
322 *AR-V9*, whereas the *AR-V7* variant was not expressed after Apa treatment
323 **(Figure 5A).**

324 In the case of 22RV1-resistant lines, 22RV1 R-ADT cells presented no significant
325 differences in *AR Total* or *AR-FL* expression compared with the untreated line. In
326 22RV1 R-ADT/E cells, a decrease in *AR Total* mRNA and a drastic increase in
327 *AR-FL* were observed. Conversely, in 22RV1 R-ADT/AA cells, exposure to Apa
328 resulted in an increase in *AR Total*. Furthermore, in all resistance models, Apa
329 treatment decreased the expression of the two variants studied, *AR-V7* and *AR-*
330 *V9* **(Figure 5B).**

331 These data suggest transcriptional reactivation of AR in the lines sensitive to Apa
332 treatment (LNCaP WT, 22RV1 WT, 22RV1 R-ADT/E and 22RV1 R-ADT/AA),
333 although this is independent of both variants studied (*AR-V7* and *AR-V9*). The
334 lines that presented cross-resistance to Apa did not present a similar pattern in
335 the expression of AR, although repression at the mRNA level of the *AR-V7* and
336 *AR-V9* variants was observed in all of them, suggesting that cross-resistance
337 could be independent of these variants.

338 To investigate the combined effects of Apa exposure on CRPC models and
339 control cell lines, we conducted a comprehensive gene expression analysis. This
340 approach allowed us to assess how Apa influences the induction of different
341 cellular phenotypes across these models. We evaluated markers associated with
342 three key phenotypes using qPCR: CSC (*Nanog*, *OCT3/4*, *SOX2*, *CD38* and
343 *CD44*), EMT (*Vimentin*, *ITGA2*, *SMAD2*, *SNAIL1* and *E-CADHERIN/CDH1*), and
344 NE (*CHGA2*, *FOXA2*, *Ki67*, *NCAM* and *NSE*).

345 In LNCaP WT cells, 5-day Apa treatment led to a pronounced upregulation of four
346 out of five CSC-related genes (*Nanog*, *SOX2*, *CD38* and *CD44*) (**Figure 6A**).
347 EMT markers also demonstrated significant changes, with *Vimentin* expression
348 increasing 30-fold and *ITGA2*, *SMAD2* and *SNAIL1* showing notable upregulation
349 (**Figure 6B**). In contrast, *E-CADHERIN* was slightly reduced, consistent with loss
350 of epithelial characteristics. Additionally, NE phenotype markers, including
351 *FOXA2*, *Ki67*, *NCAM* and *NSE*, displayed increased expression levels (**Figure**
352 **6C**). To interpret and compare the tendency towards specific phenotypes across
353 different cellular models, we created a plot illustrating the number of altered
354 genes associated with each phenotype (**Figure 6D**). This visualization helps
355 identify any skew towards particular phenotypic changes in response to Apa
356 treatment. In LNCaP WT cells, the distribution of the three studied phenotypes,
357 CSC, EMT and NE, appears to be uniformly balanced.

358 In contrast, LNCaP R-ADT cells exhibited a suppression of all CSC markers and
359 four out of five EMT genes following 5-day exposure to Apa. However, a
360 significant upregulation of NE markers, including *FOXA2*, *Ki67*, *NCAM* and *NSE*,
361 was observed (**Figure 6A-C**). The diagrammatic representation highlights a
362 distinct skew towards the NE phenotype as a result of Apa treatment (**Figure 6D,**
363 **left panel**).

364 The two LNCaP CRPC cell models exhibited markedly different expression
365 profiles. LNCaP R-ADT/E showed an upregulation of two CSC markers (*CD38*
366 and *CD44*) and two NE genes (*FOXA2* and *NCAM*) while repressing all EMT
367 genes (**Figure 6A-C**). In contrast, LNCaP R-ADT/AA demonstrated a dramatic
368 increase in all CSC markers (**Figure 6A**), a modest upregulation of two EMT
369 genes (*ITGA2* and *SNAIL1*), and a slight increase in one NE marker (*NCAM*).
370 Consequently, LNCaP R-ADT/AA cell line displayed a pronounced shift towards
371 a CSC phenotype (**Figure 6D, right panel**).

372 The gene expression profiles of 22RV1 cell lines showed distinct patterns
373 compared to LNCaP cells when treated with 0.130 mM Apa for 5 days. 22RV1
374 WT cells induced the upregulation of two CSC markers (*SOX2* and *CD38*), one
375 EMT marker (*ITGA2*), and two NE genes (*CHGA* and *FOXA2*) (**Figure 7A-C**).
376 Consequently, this cell line exhibited a balanced distribution of the three different
377 phenotypes, similarly to LNCaP WT cells (**Figure 7D**).

378 In contrast, most genes were downregulated in 22RV1 R-ADT cells, with only a
379 slight upregulation of *OCT3/4* and *NCAM* (**Figure 7A-C**). Similarly, the 22RV1 R-
380 ADT/AA cell line showed minimal changes, with *NCAM* as the only NE marker
381 significantly upregulated (**Figure 7A-C**).

382 However, the 22RV1 R-ADT/E cell line demonstrated a dramatic shift towards a
383 CSC phenotype, with four of five CSC markers (*OCT3/4*, *SOX2*, *CD38* and *CD44*)
384 upregulated while all NE markers were downregulated (**Figure 7A-C**). As a result,
385 there was a distinct skew toward the CSC phenotype following Apa exposure
386 (**Figure 7D, central panel**).

387 Our findings highlight the diverse responses among all PCa cell lines, which can
388 be attributed to their distinct resistance mechanisms and adaptations to androgen
389 deprivation, either alone or in combination with NHAs.

390

391 **Discussion:**

392 The development of NHAs has led to significant advances in the clinical
393 management of CRPC, greatly improving survival rates for PCa patients.
394 However, determining the optimal treatment sequence for CRPC remains

395 challenging owing to the potential for cross-resistance between therapies. Cross-
396 resistance, which is often a greater challenge than inherent resistance tied to
397 individual genetic profiles, evolves in response to treatments and is influenced by
398 tumor heterogeneity and clonal selection processes.

399 Cross-resistance typically arises following treatment with drugs of similar
400 mechanisms. For example, the sequential use of antiandrogens in CRPC may
401 lower the efficacy of these agents. Previous results of our group demonstrated
402 that after the establishment of R-ADT/AA resistant PCa cellular model, sequential
403 treatment with Enz did not reduce proliferation[22]). These results indicated
404 acquired cross-resistance between these NHAs have been observed in previous
405 studies on mCRPC patients[23–25]). Other studies have similarly shown that
406 CRPC cells resistant to different NHAs exhibit cross-resistance to alternative
407 treatments[26–28]).

408 In clinical recommendations for CRPC management, Apa is approved for
409 nonmetastatic CRPC following AA treatment and for the treatment of
410 mCRPC[3,29,30]). The SPARTAN clinical trial further demonstrated that Apa
411 improved metastasis-free survival in nonmetastatic CRPC patients[31]). Given
412 the structural similarity of Apa to Enz, cross-resistance is expected to develop
413 more readily following Enz exposure, with less impact following androgen
414 deprivation therapy (ADT) or AA. However, while our resistant models generally
415 presented increased Apa tolerance, the greatest tolerance was observed in the
416 LNCaP R-ADT/AA and 22RV1 R-ADT cell lines, which maintained their
417 proliferation and clonogenic capability in the presence of Apa. Consistent with our
418 findings, Zhao et al. reported that resistance to Enz or AA in CRPC models also
419 led to cross-resistance to Apa and vice versa[32]). These results suggest that
420 combining NHAs may offer advantages over sequential use in CRPC
421 management.

422 Indeed, a clinical study investigating the combination of AA and Apa in mCRPC
423 demonstrated substantial antitumor activity[33]). Sustained exposure to second-
424 line therapies in CRPC patients has been associated with resistance acquisition.
425 Moreover, greater heterogeneity in circulating tumor cells (CTCs) is correlated
426 with poorer progression and overall survival in patients treated with
427 antiandrogens. In line with these findings, we observed that Apa tolerance in

428 LNCaP-resistant models increased with prolonged drug exposure. Interestingly,
429 this effect was not detected in the 22RV1 lines; with the exception of 22RV1 R-
430 ADT cells, which presented cross-resistance to Apa, the other 22RV1 lines
431 tended to display increased sensitivity to Apa over time. This underscores the
432 high variability in treatment responses observed in clinical practice.

433 Additionally, we examined the role of the androgen receptor (AR) in response to
434 Apa. Similar to other evaluated treatments, Apa exposure in sensitive lines led to
435 AR transcriptional activation, independent of *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* variants.
436 Conversely, Zhao et al. reported that Apa treatment did not affect AR expression
437 in 22RV1 cells[32]). In our study, the LNCaP R-ADT/AA line, which was cross-
438 resistance to Apa, presented increased expression of both *AR-FL* and *AR-V9*. In
439 the Apa-treated 22RV1 R-ADT line, there was no change in *AR-FL* expression,
440 although *AR-V7* and *AR-V9* were repressed. These findings support our
441 hypothesis that resistance acquisition to NHAs is linked to increased AR
442 transcriptional activity. However, cross-resistance to additional treatments
443 prevents further AR axis suppression.

444 Tumor heterogeneity plays a critical role in the development of resistance to
445 treatments. It is well-documented that antiandrogen therapies drive processes of
446 cellular dedifferentiation and transdifferentiation, leading to the expression of
447 markers associated with EMT, NE, and CSC phenotypes(34). To explore these
448 dynamics, we evaluated the expression profiles of these markers following
449 treatment with Apa.

450 Interestingly, while both PCa WT cell lines treated with Apa exhibited a balanced
451 distribution of the three phenotypic markers, resistance models displayed
452 pronounced heterogeneity in their phenotypic profiles. This extensive variability
453 and resistance to NHAs treatments observed in our models align with findings
454 from numerous studies. Most notably, nearly all resistant cell lines demonstrated
455 an overexpression of CSC markers, supporting the hypothesis that CSCs are
456 pivotal in initiating metastasis and facilitating transitions from epithelial to
457 mesenchymal states(20,35). Similarly, the presence of NE phenotype markers
458 has been consistently identified in CRPC patients undergoing treatment with
459 various NHAs(36,37).

460 One plausible explanation for this significant phenotypic diversity could lie in the
461 clonal selection model. Substantial evidence highlights the adaptive advantage
462 of clonal selection in androgen-independent cells(38). For instance, after ADT,
463 cells exhibiting CSC characteristics may gain a proliferative edge, allowing them
464 to expand after treatment(39). Moreover, NE differentiation models suggest that
465 Neuroendocrine progenitor cells (NEPCs) may arise from the differentiation of
466 CSCs(39,40). Similarly, the EMT process has been strongly associated with
467 therapy resistance, metastasis formation, and increased disease
468 aggressiveness(41). Together, these findings underscore the complex interplay
469 of cellular phenotypes in driving therapeutic resistance and disease progression
470 in CRPC patients, suggesting that the presence of more aggressive phenotypes
471 could contribute to resistance to different treatments.

472

473 **Conclusions:**

474 The varied responses observed across different cell lines to Apa treatment
475 highlight the importance of understanding individual tumor characteristics. Each
476 patient's tumor may exhibit unique molecular features that significantly influence
477 their response to treatment, underscoring the need for personalized approaches.
478 The gene expression profiles and phenotypic changes identified in our cellular
479 models hold predictive potential, offering valuable insights into how different
480 patients may respond to therapy. These findings also emphasize the importance
481 of considering a patient's initial tumor profile, including genetic and phenotypic
482 markers, when selecting the most suitable treatment strategy.

483 Moreover, the cellular models used in this study serve as effective tools for
484 evaluating new drugs in development, shedding light on potential efficacy and
485 resistance mechanisms. The diverse responses observed across various cell
486 lines illustrate the myriad ways tumors can adapt to therapy, reinforcing the need
487 for targeted treatment approaches. By integrating these insights into clinical
488 practice, oncologists can make more informed decisions, potentially improving
489 patient outcomes and minimizing the risk of ineffective therapies. This aligns with
490 the principles of precision oncology, where treatments are tailored to the

491 molecular characteristics of each patient's tumor, paving the way for more
492 personalized and effective cancer care.

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514 **Author contributions**

515 Conceptualization: I.S., S.P. and P.J.R., methodology: I.S., S.P., J.M.S.-M. and
516 P.J.R.; validation: I.S., S.P., J.M.S.-M. and P.J.R.; formal analysis: I.S., S.P.,
517 J.M.S.-M. and P.J.R.; investigation: I.S., S.P., J.M.S.-M., G.M.-N. and J.C.-H.;
518 writing original draft: I.S., S.P. and P.J.R.; writing review and editing: I.S., S.P.,
519 J.M.S.-M., G.M.-N., J.C.-H. and P.J.R.; visualization: I.S., S.P., J.M.S.-M. and
520 P.J.R.; supervision, project administration and funding acquisition: P.J.R. All
521 authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

522 **Conflict of interest**

523 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

524

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671

672 **FIGURES LEGENDS:**

673 **Figure 1: MTT Assay for IC50 Calculation.** Determination of the 3- to 5-day
674 IC50 for Apa in the LNCaP WT cell line. The graph illustrates the percentage of
675 viable cells across the range of drug concentrations tested. The data represent
676 the mean values calculated from quadruplicate samples for each drug
677 concentration.

678

679 **Figure 2: Analysis of the Response of WT and CRPC Cellular Models to**
680 **Apalutamide Treatment.** (A) Real-time cell proliferation analysis for LNCaP cell
681 lines using the xCelligence system. The results have been standardized, with
682 untreated control cell lines set as 100% ($n=4 \pm SD$). Statistics were assessed via
683 Student's t test (statistically significant differences: ns=non-significant, ***
684 $p<0.001$). (B) Cell doubling time. Data are normalized relative to untreated cell
685 lines. Statistics were assessed via one-way ANOVA plus Dunnett's multiple
686 comparison test (statistically significant differences: **** $p<0.0001$). (C) Real-
687 time analysis of cell proliferation in 22RV1 cell lines using the xCelligence system.
688 Data have been normalized, with untreated control cell lines designated as 100%
689 ($n=4 \pm SD$). Statistics were assessed via Student's t test (statistically significant
690 differences: ns=non-significant, *** $p<0.001$). (D) Cell doubling time. Data are
691 normalized relative to untreated cell lines. Statistics were assessed via one-way
692 ANOVA plus Dunnett's multiple comparison test (statistically significant
693 differences: **** $p<0.0001$). (E) Cell cycle analysis with propidium iodide for WT
694 and CRPC cellular models untreated or treated with 0.130 μM Apa. Bar charts
695 represent the percentage of cells in different phases of the cell cycle ($n=6 \pm SD$).
696 Statistics were assessed via two-way ANOVA plus Bonferroni's multiple
697 comparisons test (statistically significant differences: * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$).

698

699

700

701

702 **Figure 3: Sequential Passage Cell Proliferation Monitoring Assay of WT and**
703 **CRPC Cellular Models Under Apalutamide Treatment.** (A) Relative cell
704 numbers after three consecutive passages in LNCaP WT and CRPC-resistant
705 models treated with 0.130 μ M Apa. (B) Corresponding analysis for 22RV1 WT
706 and CRPC-resistant cell lines. Data were normalized to untreated control cell
707 lines, which were set as 1 ($n = 3 \pm$ SD).

708

709 **Figure 4: Clonogenic Assays in PCa WT and CRPC cellular Models Treated**
710 **with Apalutamide.** (A) Representative images of colonies formed by the different
711 cell lines under the specified conditions. (B) Colony count per well. Histogram
712 data are normalized to untreated control cell lines ($n=3 \pm$ SD). (C) Colony area
713 coverage in LNCaP and 22RV1 cellular models treated with 0.130 μ M Apa.
714 Histograms show the percentage of area occupied, normalized to the
715 corresponding untreated control line ($n=3 \pm$ SD).

716

717 **Figure 5: Quantification of AR Total, AR Full length, AR-V7, and AR-V9 in**
718 **Response to Apalutamide in CRPC Cellular Models.** qPCR expression
719 analysis of AR variants in LNCaP (A) and 22RV1 (B) cell lines. Data are
720 normalized to the endogenous control (GAPDH) and expressed relative to
721 untreated cells ($n=3 \pm$ SEM).

722

723 **Figure 6: Quantification of Differentiation Markers Associated with Cancer**
724 **Stem Cells (CSC), Epithelial-to-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT) and**
725 **Neuroendocrine (NE) Traits in LNCaP WT and CRPC Cell Lines Treated with**
726 **Apalutamide.** qPCR expression analysis of CSC markers (A), EMT markers (B)
727 and NE markers (C) in LNCaP WT, LNCaP R-ADT, LNCaP R-ADT/E and LNCaP
728 R-ADT/AA after 5 days of exposure to 0.130 μ M Apa. Data are normalized to the
729 endogenous control (GAPDH) and presented relative to untreated cells ($n=3 \pm$
730 SEM). (D) Radial distribution plot illustrating the number of genes trending toward
731 differentiation-specific profiles across LNCaP R-ADT, LNCaP R-ADT/E and
732 LNCaP R-ADT/AA cell lines compared to LNCaP WT cell line.

733

734 **Figure 7: Expression Analysis of Differentiation Markers for Cancer Stem**
735 **Cells (CSC), Epithelial-to-Mesenchymal Transition (EMT), and**
736 **Neuroendocrine (NE) Traits in 22RV1 WT and CRPC Cell Lines Treated with**
737 **Apalutamide.** qPCR analysis of CSC markers (A), EMT markers (B), and NE
738 markers (C) in 22RV1 WT, 22RV1 R-ADT, 22RV1 R-ADT/E, and 22RV1 R-
739 ADT/AA cell lines after 5 days of treatment with 0.130 μ M Apa. Data are
740 normalized to the endogenous control (GAPDH) and expressed relative to
741 untreated cells ($n=3 \pm$ SEM). (D) Radial distribution plot showing the number of
742 genes aligning with differentiation-specific trends in 22RV1 R-ADT, 22RV1 R-
743 ADT/E, and 22RV1 R-ADT/AA cell lines compared to the 22RV1 WT line.

Figure 1: Simon I *et al.*

Figure 2: Simon I *et al.*

A

B

C

D

E

LNCaP

22RV1

Figure 3: Simon I *et al.*

Figure 4: Simon I *et al.*

Figure 5: Simon I *et al.*

Figure 6: Simon I *et al.*

Figure 7: Simon I *et al.*

